

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 111

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 111

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 111:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! I ^awill give thanks to the LORD with all <i>my</i> heart, In the ^bcompany of the upright and in the assembly. ² ^aGreat are the works of the LORD; <i>They are</i> ^{1b}studied by all who delight in them. ³ ^{1a}Splendid and majestic is His work, And ^bHis righteousness endures forever. ⁴ He has made His ¹wonders ²to be remembered; The LORD is ^agracious and compassionate. ⁵ He has ^agiven ¹food to those who ²fear Him; He will ^bremember His covenant forever. ⁶ He has made known to His people the power of His works, In giving them the heritage of the nations.</p>	<p>Psa. 111:1 תִּלְלוּ יְהוָה אֹדְתָה יְהוָה בְּכָל-לֵבב בְּסוֹד יְשָׁרִים וְעֵדָה : ² גְּדֹלִים מֵעֲשֵׂי יְהוָה יִדְרוּשִׁים לְכָל- חֹפְצֵיהֶם : ³ הוֹדוּ-וְהִתְרַדּוּ פְּעָלוֹ וְצִדְקָתוֹ עִמָּדֶת לְעַד : ⁴ זִכְרֵ עֲשָׂה לְנַפְלְאוֹתָיו חֲנוּן וְרַחֲמוֹם יְהוָה : ⁵ טַרְף נִתַּן לִירְאָיו יִזְכָּר לְעוֹלָם בְּרִיתוֹ : ⁶ כֶּתַח מֵעֲשֵׂי הַגִּיד לְעַמּוֹ לְתֵת לָהֶם נַחֲלַת גּוֹיִם : ⁷ מֵעֲשֵׂי יָדָיו אֲמֵת וּמִשְׁפָּט נְאֻמֹּתָם כָּל- בְּקוּדָיו : ⁸ סְמוּכִים לְעַד לְעוֹלָם עֲשׂוּיִם בְּאֵמֶת וַיִּשָּׂר : ⁹ פְּדוּת אִשְׁלַח לְעַמּוֹ צְוָה- לְעוֹלָם בְּרִיתוֹ קָדוֹשׁ וְנוֹרָא שְׁמוֹ : ¹⁰ רָאִשִׁית חֲכָמָה יִרְאֵת יְהוָה שְׁכָל טוֹב לְכָל-</p>
<p>Psa. 111:7 The works of His hands are ^{1a}truth and justice; All His precepts ^bare ²sure. ⁸ They are ^aupheld forever and ever; They are performed in ^{1b}truth and uprightness. ⁹ He has sent ^aredemption to His people; He has ¹ordained His covenant forever;</p>	<p>לְעוֹלָם אֱמֶת וְצִדְקָה וְשִׁלַּח לְעַמּוֹ צְוָה- לְעוֹלָם בְּרִיתוֹ קָדוֹשׁ וְנוֹרָא שְׁמוֹ : ¹⁰ רָאִשִׁית חֲכָמָה יִרְאֵת יְהוָה שְׁכָל טוֹב לְכָל-</p>

<p>^bHoly and ²awesome is His name. ¹⁰ The ^{1a}fear of the LORD is the beginning of wisdom; A ^bgood understanding have all those who ²do <i>His commandments</i>; His ^cpraise endures forever.</p>	<p>עֲשִׂיהֶם יִתְהַלְּלוּ עַמְּךָ לְעַד :</p>
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References

Psalm 111:1

¹Or *Hallelujah! I will*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 35:18; 138:1

^bPs 89:7; 149:1

Psalm 111:2

¹Lit *sought out*

^aPs 92:5

^bPs 143:5

Psalm 111:3

¹Lit *Splendor and majesty*

^aPs 96:6; 145:5

^bPs 112:3, 9; 119:142

Psalm 111:4

¹I.e. wonderful acts

²Lit *a memorial*

^aPs 86:5, 15; 103:8; 145:8

Psalm 111:5

¹Lit *prey*

²Or *revere*

^aMatt 6:31-33

^bPs 105:8

Psalm 111:7

¹Or *faithfulness*

²Or *trustworthy*

^aRev 15:3

^bPs 19:7; 93:5

Psalm 111:8

¹Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 119:160; Is 40:8; Matt 5:18

^bPs 19:9

Psalm 111:9

¹Lit *commanded*

²I.e. inspiring reverence

^aLuke 1:68

^bPs 99:3; Luke 1:49

Psalm 111:10

¹Or *reverence for*

²Lit *do* them

^aJob 28:28; Prov 1:7; 9:10; Eccl 12:13

^bPs 119:98; Prov 3:4

^cPs 145:2

Targum

Psa. 111:1 Hallelujah! I will sing praise in the presence of the LORD with all my heart in the secret of the upright and the assembly. ² The deeds of the LORD are great; they are sought for by all who desire them. ³ His work is praise and glory, and his merit endures for ever. ⁴ He made a good memorial for his wonders; the LORD is gracious and merciful. ⁵ He gave food to those who fear him; he will remember his covenant forever. ⁶ The might of his deeds he told to his people, to give them the inheritance of the Gentiles. ⁷ The works of his hands are truth and justice; all his commands are faithful. ⁸ They are reliable for ever and ever; they are done in truth and uprightness. ⁹ He sent redemption to his people; he commanded his covenant for ever; his name is holy and awesome. ¹⁰ The beginning of wisdom is fear of the LORD, good understanding to all who do them; his praise endures forever.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Sage Sforno said this Psalm is a sermon exhorting the ordinary Jew to devote time to Torah study. The uneducated person usually uses one of the following reasons for not studying the Torah: it is too difficult, or their livelihood takes up all their time. The Psalmist responds to these excuses by telling the people that they need to be indebted to the LORD for the kindness from the Sefirah Chesed. The best way to thank the LORD is to study Torah. The beginning of wisdom is a reverence for the LORD. This is done through the execution of the mitzvot in the Torah.

Notes on the Psalm

The English versions like to say “fear of the LORD.” The translation “reverence” is preferable in a spiritual awareness sense. The idea of fear says that the LORD will take vengeance on His people if they do not follow him. Jewish parents use the fear of the LORD to scold their children. The adult becomes fearful of the LORD’s retribution when this is done. This attitude tends to drive adults away from the LORD. It is not pleasant to imagine an angry God watching every move a person makes.

It is better to show reverence. This Psalm says that a person demonstrates reverence to the LORD by following the Torah and performing the mitzvot. The LORD created everything in the Universe. The LORD deserves reverence and gratitude.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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